

Analysis of Transmission Line Arrangement Efficiency Based on Electric Field Calculation of Conductors Using Computational Simulations

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Abstract — High Surge Impedance Loading (HSIL) lines are transmission lines with modified arrangements designed to maximize their power transmission capacity. Factors that contribute to increasing the surge impedance loading of these lines include the electric field distribution on the transmission line conductor, the voltage level, the equalization and maximization of surface electric fields of the sub-conductors in each phase, and the increase in the number of sub-conductors per phase. This work aims to analyze 5 different arrangements used in HSIL lines and determine which arrangement is the most efficient in terms of electric field distribution. The results will be calculated through computational simulations using the Finite Element Method (FEM). Additionally, a visual representation of the electric field distribution on the conductors is presented. This study aims to highlight the potential of using computational simulations for electrical analysis in transmission lines..

Keywords: *Electric Field, Efficiency, HSIL, FEM, computational Simulation.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The growing need to transmit large blocks of power through high-voltage transmission lines (TLs), coupled with economic and environmental constraints on the construction of new lines, has driven development towards the optimization of high-power transmission systems. Among the studies in this area, the concept of High Surge Impedance Loading (HSIL) lines has gained significant attention.

This technology operates on the principle that the conductor bundle arrangements in conventional transmission lines reduce project efficiency [1]–[4]. Thus, the technique involves rearranging or increasing the number of sub-conductors per phase to achieve a more equalized distribution of the electric field generated by the transmission line (TL), aiming to decrease energy losses due to the corona effect and consequently increase the line's power capacity [5]–[7].

The electric field distribution in a transmission line is a function of several parameters, including the applied voltage, tower configuration, spacing between conductors within each phase, and conductor size. Once the surface electric field on the conductors is determined, the arrangement of sub-conductors can be modified to alter the potential gradient of the electric

field, thereby minimizing it and contributing to an increase in the efficiency of an HSIL line.

In this context, various numerical methods can be employed to determine the electric field in transmission lines. Among these, the Finite Element Method (FEM) stands out as a powerful numerical tool for obtaining discretized solutions in a finite space [8]. Thus, in this article, the electric field in 5 different transmission tower arrangements currently used in High Surge Impedance Loading lines in Brazil will be calculated using computational tools based on the Finite Element Method. The primary objective of this work is to, based on the electric field values on each conductor, determine which arrangement is the most efficient, meaning which arrangement exhibits the best electric field distribution..

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Specifications of the Arrangements

For this study, five transmission tower arrangements employed in 500 kV HSIL lines were utilized. The conductor diameter values were obtained from [9], while the phase-to-phase distances and the distances between sub-conductors within each phase for the five arrangements were sourced from [10].

The initial stage of the work involved the creation of a graphical representation of the conductors. To simplify the analyses, the tower structure itself was not explicitly modeled. Figures 1 through 5 illustrate the schematic drawings of the studied arrangements. The distances between the sub-conductors and between the phases are represented in meters in these figures.

Fig. 1. Arrangement 1 - Cross Rope Tower

Fig. 5. Arranjo 5. Torre cara de gato.

The parameters of the 5 studied arrangements are shown in detail in Table I.

TABLE I: PARAMETERS OF THE ARRANGEMENTS.

Arrangement Type	Sub-conductor Spacing per Phase (m)	Phase-to-Phase Spacing (m)	Conductor Height Above Ground (m)
<i>Cross rope</i>	0,457	5	10
Symmetrical Expanded Bundle	1,2	10	10
Single Mast	0,9	6	10 (Phases A and C) and 17,55 (Phases B)
Racket	0,457	5	10 (Phases A and C) e 14 (Phases B)
Cat Face	1,2	10	10 (fases A and C) e 14 (Phases B)

Fig. 2. Arrangement 2 - Symmetrical Expanded Bundle Towersimétrico.

Fig. 3. Arrangement 3 - Single Mast Tower.

Fig. 4. Arranjo 4. Torre raquete.

B. Computational Simulationss

To perform the simulations using the Finite Element Method (FEM), a dedicated module within the COMSOL Multiphysics® software was utilized, applying Maxwell's equations to calculate the electric field at a specific spatial location. Two materials were defined: air to represent the surrounding medium and aluminum for the conductors. The simulations were conducted using the peak voltage values of the tower's operating voltage to analyze the worst-case electric field conditions. These values are detailed in Table II.

TABLE II: VOLTAGE VALUES APPLIED TO THE PHASES.

Phase	Voltage (kV)
A	$500.000 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot e^{-2\pi \frac{j}{3}}$
B	$500.000 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}}$
C	$500.000 \cdot \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot e^{2\pi \frac{j}{3}}$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONOS

In this section, the graphs with the electric field distribution in the 5 considered arrangements are presented. The results can be seen in Figs. 6 to 10.

Fig. 6. Electric field distribution for Arrangement 1. Cross Rope Tower. Electric field values in kV/cm.

Fig. 7. Electric field distribution for Arrangement 2. Symmetrical Expanded Bundle Tower. Electric field values in kV/cm.

Fig. 8. Electric field distribution for Arrangement 3. Single Mast Tower. Electric field values in kV/cm.

Fig. 9. Electric field distribution for Arrangement 4. Racket Tower. Electric field values in kV/cm.

Fig. 10. Electric field distribution for Arrangement 5. Cat Face Tower. Electric field values in kV/cm.

Observing Figs. 6 to 10, it is possible to verify at which points of the arrangement the electric field is more intense. Furthermore, the influence of the distances between the sub-conductors and between the phases on the resulting configuration of the electric field is noticed. In fact, even the arrangements with similar formats (rectangular in the case of the cross rope and symmetrical expanded bundle arrangements) and (triangular in the case of the single mast, racket and cat face arrangements) presented distinct distributions and different values of electric field.

The graphs with the values of the maximum electric field on the surface of each of the sub-conductors of the 3 phases, for each of the 5 arrangements studied, are presented below. In Fig. 11, it is shown how each sub-conductor was numbered. The numbering order was used in all the arrangements and was always maintained following from left to right and clockwise.

Fig. 11. Numbering of the sub-conductors of each phase ('fase'). Example for Arrangement 1. Cross Rope Tower.

From Fig. 12 to Fig. 16, the electric field values calculated for each sub-conductor of each arrangement studied are shown.

Fig. 12. Electric field values (kV/cm) for the subconductors of arrangement 1.

Fig. 13. Electric field strengths (kV/cm) for the subconductors of the configuration 2.

Fig. 14. Electric field values (kV/cm) for the subconductors of the arrangement 3.

Fig. 15. Electric field values (kV/cm) for the subconductors of arrangement 4.

Fig. 16. Subconductor electric field levels (kV/cm) for bundle arrangement 5.

It is possible to observe that in all arrangements, the conductors of phase B (the middle phase) exhibit high electric

field values. This is likely due to the influence of the phases located at the extremities of the arrangement (phases A and C).

Box I summarizes some relevant parameters derived from the calculated electric field values on the subconductors. Although arrangement 1 (cross rope tower) has the lowest electric field value per conductor, arrangement 3 (monopole tower) has a better electric field distribution, considering that this arrangement presented the lowest average electric field.

BOX I – RESUMO DOS VALORES DE CAMPO ELÉTRICO DOS SUBCONDUTORES.

Electric field (kV/cm)	Arranjo 1	Arranjo 2	Arranjo 3	Arranjo 4	Arranjo 5
Minimum	17,25	18,22	17,46	17,74	18,34
Maximum	23,65	22,84	21,37	22,32	22,03
Average Phase A	19,28	19,54	19,18	19,58	19,81
Média Fase B	21,79	21,61	18,92	20,49	20,72
Média Fase C	19,46	19,85	19,34	19,77	20,01
Média 3 Fases	20,18	20,33	19,15	19,95	20,21

IV. CONCLUSIONSS

Nesse trabalho, In this work, several EHVTL (Extra-High Voltage Transmission Line) arrangements were analyzed considering the behavior of the electric field in each topology, which was calculated using the finite element method applied to a two-dimensional model.

Arrangements 1 and 2 have similarities in both topology and the results obtained, where it is observed that the phase-to-phase distance is symmetrical at ground level for the three phases, as well as between phases. For both situations, the distances are less than 11 m.

The best results were obtained in arrangement 3, with a symmetrical topology between the distances of phases A and C in relation to ground level with a distance of 10 m, and asymmetrical for the central phase with a distance of 17.55 m. In this configuration, the best results were obtained, as the central phase had a reduction in the average electric field value compared to arrangements 1, 2, and 5.

In the simulated results, it was possible to verify that the reduction of the electric field depends on the distances between phases and phase-to-ground. The central phase presented higher values because it is influenced by the phases at the extremities.

In arrangements 1 and 2, the resulting electric field values are technically equal, because the distance in this topology was not sufficient to reduce the electric field.

For the arrangements in which the phase-to-ground distance is greater, considerable results were only observed when there

was a significant increase in the distance between phases and phase-to-ground.

Arrangement 3 proved to be more efficient, as it reduced the influence of the central phase on the outer phases, which resulted in a better distribution of the three-phase electric field, directly contributing to the balanced reduction of losses, resulting in the expansion of the EHVTL capacity.

The positive impact on the reduction of losses due to the electric field effect is significant, mainly due to the high dimension of the power to be transferred in 500 kV lines.

For future work, other factors that influence losses will be considered, such as phase sequence, the number of subconductors, aspects related to electromagnetic compatibility, and safety standards in the right-of-way.servidão.

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